

ISic0188

I.Sicily inscription 0188

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Date and place of discovery not recorded

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 59

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 37 cm

Width 45.5 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ex d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

2. locus M(arci) Iuli(i)

3. Dionysi

Apparatus

Text from ILTermini

Translation (en)

By decree of the town council, burial plot of Marcus Iulius Dionysus

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175701

EDR 077919

EDCS 8900397

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0519

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 110

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere e Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 544 no.7 tav.4

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0188. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334482>